

Field experiment of cement-modified loess

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Abstract. The construction of a compacted and stabilized layer with local soil from the excavation, mixed with Portland cement, is a soil improvement technique widely applied in foundation works in collapsible loess ground in Bulgaria. Commonly, the role of that cement-modified layer is to replace a part of the collapsible ground, to increase the bearing capacity of the soil base, and/or to be an engineering barrier against migration of harmful substances in the geoenvironment.

A multi-barrier near-surface short-lived low- and intermediate-level radioactive waste repository is under construction in Bulgaria. A cement-modified soil layer beneath the disposal cells is going to be built by *in-situ* compacted mixture of local loess and Portland cement. The cement-modified layer (indicated as loess-cement cushion) is not a continuation of the foundation, but it is a part of the soil base and performs two main functions: to be an engineering barrier against eventual migration of radionuclides in the geoenvironment and to increase the bearing capacity to restrict differential settlement of the soil base.

The present paper describes a field experiment aiming to verify the strength and deformation characteristics of a selected optimum loess–cement mixture by implementation of *in-situ* cement-modified loess ground. After 28-day curing at *in-situ* conditions, the loess-cement did not exhibit any fissuring or other disturbances. The allowable bearing capacity q_a of the cement-modified loess ground exceeded 900 kN/m², and it possessed the following strength and deformation characteristics: deformation (plate) modulus $E_{PLT} = 500$ MPa; coefficient of sub-grade reaction $k_s = 2158$ MPa/m, and unconfined compressive strength $q_u = 2.00$ MPa.

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INTRODUCTION

In Bulgaria, a soil improvement technique widely applied in foundation works in collapsible loess ground is the construction of a compacted and stabilized layer with local soil from the excavation, mixed with Portland cement. Ordinarily, the role of that cement-modified layer is to replace a part of the collapsible ground, to increase the bearing capacity of the soil base, and/or to be an engineering barrier against migration of harmful substances in the geoenvironment (Evstatiev and Karastanev, 2013).

A multi-barrier near-surface short-lived low- and intermediate-level radioactive waste repository is under construction in Bulgaria. A cement-modified soil layer (indicated as loess-cement cushion) beneath the disposal cells is going to be built by *in-situ* compacted mixture of local loess and Portland cement. The cement-modified layer is not a continuation of the foundation, but it is a part of the soil base and performs two main functions: to be an engineering barrier against eventual migration of radionuclides in the geoenvironment (including by increasing the thickness of the aeration zone beneath the disposal cells) and to increase the bearing

capacity in order to restrict differential settlement of the soil base.

The optimum cement content of the loess-cement layer beneath the radioactive waste repository was defined to be 5% (by the dry weight of soil) of Portland cement type CEM I 42.5 N – SR 5. The selection was based on a particular classification and physico-mechanical tests of a set of loess-cement mixtures (Karastanev *et al.*, 2016). Laboratory measurements of the geotechnical parameters showed that the selected loess-cement mixture, prepared at W_{opt} and ρ_{ds} after proper curing, possesses strength and deformation characteristics that fully meet the design stress-strain requirements to the soil-cement cushion beneath the repository foundation (Tchakalova and Karastanev, 2017).

The present paper describes a field experiment aiming to verify the strength and deformation characteristics of the selected optimum loess-cement mixture by implementation of *in-situ* cement-modified loess ground.

TEST SITE AND MATERIALS USED

The test site for the field experiment of cement-modified loess ground is located in the area of the

town of Kozloduy, Northwest Bulgaria. An excavation for obtaining the necessary local loess was prepared before starting the construction of the *in-situ* cement-modified loess ground. Beneath the humus layer (1.0–1.2 m), a root system zone developed underneath, with a thickness of about 0.6–0.8 m, was established, which was considered unsuitable for loess-cement construction. Finally, an excavation was made, with bottom dimensions 20.5×5.5 m and a depth of 3.0–3.2 m, from the ground surface level along the southern side and 2.6–2.8 m along the northern side (Fig. 1). In total, about 185 m³ of local loess were extracted for the construction of the experimental cement-modified ground. The preparation of the excavation was completed by leveling and compaction of the bottom by rolling.

The classification characteristics of the excavated loess were determined in compliance with the respective ASTM procedures as follows: grain-size composition, according to ASTM D 422–63; specific gravity, according to ASTM D 854; and plasticity limits, in accordance with ASTM D 4318. The summarized classification characteristics of the used loess were defined as follows:

- Classification symbol and designation according to USCS: CL – lean clay
- Classification designation according to Minikov (1968): typical loess

Fig. 1. Plan and cross-section of the excavation with the cement-modified loess ground and locations of plate loading tests (PLT)

- Particle size distribution:

>4.75 mm	0%
4.75–0.075 mm	10%
<0.075 mm	90%
- Specific gravity: 2.74
- Liquid limit *LL*: 31.3%
- Plastic limit *PL*: 19.0%
- Plasticity index *PI*: 12.3%

CONSTRUCTION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL CEMENT-MODIFIED LOESS GROUND

For the construction of the cement-modified loess ground, the mixture was prepared in a stationary counter-flow mixer with a capacity up to 1 m³.

The water content *W* and bulk density ρ of the loose stock-piled loess soil were determined before starting the mixing. The repeated measurements of samples from the stock-piled loess in loose state yielded values within the following range:

- Water content $W = 12.0\text{--}12.5\%$;
- bulk density $\rho = 1.05\text{--}1.07 \text{ g/cm}^3$.

The quantities of loess, Portland cement and water, necessary for one filling of the mixer, were determined on the basis of these values. In view of reaching the optimum water content $W_{opt} = 17.0\%$ of the ready loess-cement mixture (with 5% of Portland cement), as determined previously (Karastanev *et al.*, 2016), and taking into account the atmospheric conditions during the cushion construction, the following quantities of the ingredients were defined for one mixer charging:

- stock-piled loess in loose state – 885 kg

- Portland cement type CEM I
42,5 N – SR 5 – 37.5 kg
- added water – 50 L

The determined quantities of loess and cement were loaded simultaneously in the mixer and homogenized in a “dry” state (with the natural water content of loess) for one minute. After adding the prescribed amount of water, mixing proceeded for another 2–3 minutes, until complete homogenization was achieved. The ready mix was immediately transported by tip trucks to the test site. In order to comply with the requirement for compaction of the mixture not later than 4 hours after blending of loess and cement, it was estimated that about 20–21 m³ of freely dumped mixture are necessary to perform one layer of compacted soil-cement with a thickness of 10–12 cm.

The spreading and leveling of the dumped mixture were carried out using an excavator shovel (Fig. 2a). The compaction was implemented by a VV–110 single steel drum roller with an operation weight of about 12 t (Fig. 2b). Six roller runs (passing along the same track) were necessary to achieve 96–100% of the design bulk density ($\rho = 2.02 \text{ g/cm}^3$). Each next layer was placed immediately after completion and validation of the parameters of the previous one. At the end of each working day, the last compacted soil-cement layer was covered with a polyethylene foil in order to ensure the required optimum moisture for the proper hardening of the loess-cement.

Nine layers with a total thickness of about 1 m were built according to the described technology. The ready experimental cement-modified loess ground (Fig. 3) was covered with a protective soil

Fig. 2. Construction of the cement-modified loess ground: a) spreading and leveling of the dumped loess-cement mixture; b) compaction of the loess-cement mixture.

Fig. 3. Completed experimental cement-modified loess ground.

layer (0.3–0.4 m thick) to ensure optimal conditions for curing and hydration of Portland cement.

CONTROL ACTIVITIES AND TESTS

Control activities during construction

The following main factors and characteristics were controlled during the construction of the experimental cement-modified loess ground:

- quantities of initial materials (loess, Portland cement and water) for each mixer charge;
- degree of homogenization of the mixture;
- water content of the mixture delivered in the experimental site;

- bulk density and water content of each compacted soil-cement layer;
- protection against drying for ensuring proper curing conditions.

The determined quantities of loess, Portland cement and water for one charging of the mixer were controlled by a dozer system of the mixing plant. Before entering the mixer, the loess was let pass through sieves, which provided a very high degree of fragmentation. The technology of mixing the initial materials, as described above, ensured a well-homogenous mixture with a uniform color, without spots of non-homogenized cement.

The moisture of the ready loess-cement mixture was controlled by sampling for water content (according to a standard weight method – ASTM D 2216) from each tip truck delivered mixture in the experimental site. The water content varied within the range of 17.0–19.0%. Values a bit higher than the optimum water content ($W_{opt} = 17.0\%$) predominated. In view of the atmospheric conditions during spreading and leveling, the water content of the completed soil-cement, as will be seen hereinafter, is close to the optimum one.

After the compaction of each layer was accomplished, control samples were extracted using a cutting ring with a volume of 585 cm³ to determine the bulk density (and consequently the water content) of the completed soil-cement layer in compliance with ASTM D 2937 (Fig. 4). The degree of compaction was considered sufficient when at least 96% of the design bulk density $\rho = 2.02$ g/cm³ was reached,

Fig. 4. Extraction of control samples with a cutting ring for determination of the bulk density: a) ramming; b) taking out the cutting ring.

i.e., the value of the compaction coefficient $k_{comp} \geq 0.96$ was reached.

With respect to the protection against drying during the construction, as already mentioned above, each subsequent layer was placed immediately after completion and validation of the parameters of the previous one, and at the end of each working day the last compacted soil-cement layer was covered with a polyethylene foil.

Control tests after 28-day curing

After 28-day curing of the experimental cement-modified loess ground, the following control tests were conducted: plate loading test (PLT); unconfined compressive strength (UCS). The plate loading tests were conducted in accordance with BDS EN 1997-2 and BDS 8004.

Three plate loading tests were carried out on the cement-modified loess ground. Their locations are shown in Fig. 1.

The protective soil cover above the loess-cement was removed in three places in order to conduct the plate loading tests and restored after the tests were done. In the three places, it was established that there were no cracks, fissures, or any other disturbances on the cushion surface as a result of shrinkage due to drying or other processes (Fig. 5a).

The tests were done by plate loading equipment comprising a rigid circular plate with a diameter of 300 mm and a hydraulic jack with maximum load

capacity of 500 kN, *i.e.*, with the ability of plate loading up to 7 MN/m^2 . The load was recorded directly from the display of the jack with an accuracy of 0.1 N. The settlement was measured by means of three digital indicators for displacement (with an accuracy of 0.01 mm) placed on the plate and fixed by electromagnets to a rigid frame. A truck total weight of 20 t was used as a counterweight during the tests (Fig. 5b) so that the maximum pressure during plate loading reached 900 kN/m^2 with equal loading steps of 100 kN/m^2 .

The results of the performed three plate loading tests are given in Fig. 6. The presented load–settlement $S = f(P)$ diagrams show clearly that, up to the maximum applied pressure of 900 kN/m^2 , the ultimate bearing capacity of the loess-cement q_{ult} was not reached. The direct extrapolation of the results of the plate loading test to the actual stress–strain state of the foundation is not a standardized procedure, but it is recommended and used in practice (Bowles, 1996). The analysis of the results of the plate loading tests shows that, in this case, the allowable (design) bearing capacity $q_a (R_a)$ of the cement-modified loess ground could be assumed as exceeding 900 kN/m^2 .

The deformation (plate) modulus E_{PLT} (for the pressure range of $400\text{--}600 \text{ kN/m}^2$) is determined based on the plate loading tests according to BDS EN 1997-2 and BDS 8004 as well as the coefficient of subgrade reaction k_s according to BDS EN 1997-2. The obtained results are summarized in Table 1. The average value of E_{PLT} is 500 MPa.

Fig. 5. (a) Surface of the cement-modified loess ground after 28-day curing beneath the protective soil cover; (b) Conducting plate loading test (PLT-2).

Fig. 6. Load–settlement $S = f(P)$ diagrams from plate loading tests performed on the cement-modified loess ground after 28-day curing.

The other control testing was the determination of the UCS q_u after 28-day curing of five control samples extracted from different layers of the cement-modified loess ground immediately after their compaction. The control samples were kept for 28 days in a climatic chamber in the rings themselves. The UCS was determined after immersion in water for 4 hours of cured test specimens. The test was conducted with cylindrical specimens with $d:h \approx 1:1$, using a compression machine at a loading rate of 1 mm/min and permanent digital recording of loading and deformation.

The stress–strain plots of the performed UCS tests are shown in Fig. 7. The q_u values after respective correction factors according to ASTM C 42 due to the ratio $d:h \approx 1:1$ of the test specimens were within the range of 1.94–2.08 MPa, the average value being 2.00 MPa. The test specimens of the optimum loess-cement mixture prepared at W_{opt} and ρ_{ds} in laboratory conditions after 28-day curing showed about 10% higher $q_u = 2.27$ MPa (Tchakalova and Karastanev, 2017), which is normal in view of the

Fig. 7. Stress–strain plots from the UCS tests of cement-modified loess samples ($d:h \approx 1:1$) after 28-day curing.

Table 1
Values of the deformation (plate) modulus E_{PLT} and the coefficient of subgrade reaction k_s of the experimental cement-modified loess ground (for the pressure range of 0.4–0.6 MPa)

Test No	Deformation modulus		Coefficient of subgrade reaction
	BDS 8004	BDS EN 1997-2	
	E_{PLT} , MPa	E_{PLT} , MPa	k_s , MPa/m
PLT-1	503.88	501.74	2166.06
PLT-2	536.82	534.55	2307.69
PLT-3	465.25	463.27	2000.00
Average, X_{mean}	501.98	499.85	2157.92

technological peculiarities of field and laboratory soil-cement preparation.

CONCLUSION

A field experiment of cement-modified loess ground was executed to justify *in-situ* the strength and deformation characteristics of the selected optimum loess-cement mixture for construction of a loess-cement cushion beneath the disposal cells of a radioactive waste repository. The loess-cement mixture was prepared with local loess and 5% of Portland cement CEM I 42,5 N – SR 5 in a stationary mixer and compacted at W_{opt} and ρ_{ds} . After 28-

day curing at *in-situ* conditions, the loess-cement did not exhibit any fissuring or other disturbances. The allowable bearing capacity q_a of the cement-modified loess ground exceeded 900 kN/m², and it possessed the following strength and deformation characteristics: deformation (plate) modulus $E_{PLT} = 500$ MPa; coefficient of sub-grade reaction $k_s = 2158$ MPa/m, unconfined compressive strength $q_u = 2.00$ MPa.

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ABBREVIATIONS AND SYMBOLS

ASTM	American Association of for Testing and Materials
BDS EN	Bulgarian State Standard European Norm
USCS	Unified Soil Classification System

E_{PLT}	plate modulus, MPa
k_s	coefficient of sub-grade reaction, MPa/m
LL	liquid limit, %
PL	plastic limit, %
PI	plasticity index, %
q_a	Allowable bearing capacity, kN/m ²
q_u	unconfined compressive strength (UCS), MPa
W_{opt}	optimum water content, %
ρ_{ds}	standard (maximum) dry density, g/cm ³

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